

Projection Retrieval: Theory and Algorithms

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Abstract—We consider the fundamental problem of determining a low-rank orthogonal projection operator P from measurements of the form $\|Px\|$. First, we leverage a nonembedding result for the complex Grassmannian to establish and analyze a lower bound on the number of measurements necessary to uniquely determine every possible P . Next, we provide a collection of particularly few measurement vectors that uniquely determine almost every P . Finally, we propose manifold-constrained least-squares optimization as a general technique for projection retrieval.

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper considers the fundamental problem of reconstructing an orthogonal projection operator $P: \mathbb{C}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^d$ of rank r from norm measurements $\{\|Px_i\|\}_{i=1}^n$, where each x_i is a known vector in \mathbb{C}^d . In the special case where $r = 1$, this is equivalent to the phase retrieval problem of recovering a unit vector $u \in \mathbb{C}^d$ up to global phase from intensity measurements $\{|\langle u, x_i \rangle|\}_{i=1}^n$ [3]. Indeed, in this case we may write $P = uu^*$, and so

$$\|Px_i\|^2 = x_i^* P^* P x_i = x_i^* P x_i = x_i^* u u^* x_i = |\langle u, x_i \rangle|^2.$$

This setting in which u is known to have unit norm finds application in the quantum tomography of pure states. Similarly, the more general case of rank- r projections is applicable when the unknown state is known to be maximally mixed within some unknown r -dimensional subspace [11].

This generalization of phase retrieval is dual in some sense to another projection-based generalization: so-called phase retrieval by projections [7]. There, the goal is to recover a vector up to global phase from norms of projections, that is, the projections are used to measure an unknown vector, whereas our setting uses vectors to measure an unknown projection. The problem we consider can also be viewed as a phase retrieval-type analog to the sampling of operators studied by Pfander [12]. There, the idea is to interrogate an unknown operator of some known form with only a few functions, and then reliably determine the operator from the outputs. Our setting is similar, except we only have access to the norms of the outputs.

In the following section, we leverage a nonembedding result for the complex Grassmannian [14] to establish a lower bound on the number of measurements necessary to uniquely determine every possible orthogonal projection of rank r . This bound has a lower-order term that we estimate in different

regimes so as to better understand what the bound offers. In Section III, we provide a collection of particularly few measurement vectors that uniquely determine almost every orthogonal projection of rank r . This collection follows from a polarization-type trick inspired by [1]. Section IV proposes manifold-constrained least-squares optimization as a general technique for projection retrieval. Here, we discuss simulation results gotten using a freely available manifold-constrained optimization toolbox on Matlab called Manopt [6]; the simulations demonstrate the feasibility of our technique for projection retrieval. Finally, we discuss remaining open problems in Section V.

II. NECESSARY CONDITION FOR INJECTIVITY

Let $\text{Gr}(r, \mathbb{C}^d) = \text{U}(d)/(\text{U}(r) \times \text{U}(d-r))$ denote the complex Grassmannian, i.e., the smooth manifold of r -dimensional subspaces of \mathbb{C}^d . This manifold has $2r(d-r)$ real dimensions. By Whitney's embedding theorem, any smooth manifold of real dimension m can be smoothly embedded into \mathbb{R}^{2m} . The following provides a converse of this result for the complex Grassmannian:

Theorem 1 (Main Theorem in [14]). *If the complex Grassmannian $\text{Gr}(r, \mathbb{C}^d)$ smoothly embeds into \mathbb{R}^n , then*

$$n > 4r(d-r) - 2 \sum_{i=1}^r (\alpha(d-i) - \alpha(i-1)), \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha(i)$ denotes the number of 1s in the binary expansion of i .

It turns out that $\{\|Px_i\|\}_{i=1}^n$ provides complete information only if it produces a smooth embedding of the complex Grassmannian into Euclidean space. Indeed, consider the following lifting-type argument (cf. [2]):

$$\begin{aligned} \|Px\|^2 &= x^* P^* P x \\ &= x^* P x = \text{Tr}[x^* P x] = \text{Tr}[x x^* P] = \langle P, x x^* \rangle_{\text{HS}}. \end{aligned}$$

Then complete information of the form $\{\|Px_i\|\}_{i=1}^n$ is equivalent to complete information of the form $\{\langle P, x_i x_i^* \rangle_{\text{HS}}\}_{i=1}^n$, and so the following result applies:

Theorem 2 (Theorem 5 and Lemma 1 in [11]). *Any mapping of the form $P \mapsto \{\langle P, A_i \rangle_{\text{HS}}\}_{i=1}^n$ that is injective over all rank- r orthogonal projection operators P over \mathbb{C}^d necessarily produces a smooth embedding of the complex Grassmannian $\text{Gr}(r, \mathbb{C}^d)$ into \mathbb{R}^n .*

Combining the above theorems and estimating the summation term in (1) then produces the following corollary:

Corollary 3. *If $P \mapsto \{\|Px_i\|\}_{i=1}^n$ is injective over all rank- r orthogonal projection operators P over \mathbb{C}^d , then*

$$n > 4r(d-r) - e(r, d),$$

where $e(r, d)$ satisfies the following estimates:

- (i) $e(r, d) \leq 2r \left(\log_2 d - \Omega(\log_2 r) \right)$,
- (ii) $e(r, d) \geq 2r \left(\log_2 d - O(\log_2 r) \right)$ when d has the form $d = 2^k - 1$, and
- (iii) $e(r, d) = 2r$ when d has the form $d = 2^k + r$, $2^k \geq r$.

Here, $\Omega(\cdot)$ and $O(\cdot)$ denote big-Omega and big-O notation, respectively.

Proof: It suffices to find bounds on the summation term in (1). For (i), we first note that $\alpha(d-i) \leq \log_2 d + 1$ for each i . Also, letting $\alpha_j(i)$ denote the j th bit of the binary expansion of i and taking $c := \lfloor \log_2 r \rfloor$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^{r-1} \alpha(i) &\geq \sum_{i=0}^{2^c-1} \sum_{j=1}^c \alpha_j(i) \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^c \sum_{i=0}^{2^c-1} \alpha_j(i) = c \cdot 2^{c-1} \geq \frac{1}{4} r (\log_2 r - 1). \end{aligned}$$

Putting everything together, we then have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^r \left(\alpha(d-i) - \alpha(i-1) \right) &\leq r(\lfloor \log_2 d \rfloor + 1) - \frac{1}{4} r (\log_2 r - 1) \\ &\leq r \left(\log_2 d - \Omega(\log_2 r) \right), \end{aligned}$$

thereby implying (i). For (ii), notice that $d = 2^k - 1$ implies

$$\alpha(i) + \alpha(d-i) = \alpha(d),$$

since there are no carries when adding $i + (d-i)$ in binary. As such,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^r \left(\alpha(d-i) - \alpha(i-1) \right) &= \alpha(d-r) + \sum_{i=1}^{r-1} \left(\alpha(i) + \alpha(d-i) \right) - 2 \sum_{i=1}^{r-1} \alpha(i) \\ &= \left(\alpha(d) - \alpha(r) \right) + (r-1)\alpha(d) - 2 \sum_{i=1}^{r-1} \alpha(i) \\ &\geq r \log_2 d - 2 \sum_{i=1}^r \alpha(i). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we observe that $\alpha(i) \leq \log_2 r + 1$ whenever $i \leq r-1$ to get the result. For (iii), we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^r \left(\alpha(d-i) - \alpha(i-1) \right) = \sum_{i=1}^r \alpha(2^k + r - i) - \sum_{i=1}^r \alpha(i-1).$$

Changing variables with $j := r - i$ in the first sum and $j := i - 1$ in the second then gives

$$\sum_{i=1}^r \left(\alpha(d-i) - \alpha(i-1) \right) = \sum_{j=0}^{r-1} \left(\alpha(2^k + j) - \alpha(j) \right).$$

At this point, we observe that there are no carries when adding $2^k + j$ in binary since $2^k \geq r > j$. As such, $\alpha(2^k + j) - \alpha(j) = \alpha(2^k) = 1$, thereby implying (iii). ■

Notice that in the case where $r = 1$, the dominant term of the lower bound (1) becomes $4d - 4$. In phase retrieval, it is conjectured that $4d - 4$ measurements are necessary and generically sufficient for injectivity [4], [9]. No conjecture has yet been formulated for the corresponding number of measurements for projection retrieval.

Before concluding this section, we remark that if P can be recovered using measurement vectors $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^n$, then so can $I - P$. Indeed, one may convert measurements of $I - P$ into measurements of P :

$$\|Px_i\|^2 = \|x_i\|^2 - \|(I - P)x_i\|^2.$$

Then after recovering P from these measurements, simply subtract it from I to get $I - P$. As such, perhaps surprisingly, the minimum number of measurements required to uniquely determine rank- r projections will be the same for rank- $(d-r)$ projections. Along these lines, it is straightforward to verify that (1) remains unchanged when replacing r with $d-r$.

III. SUFFICIENT CONDITION FOR ALMOST INJECTIVITY

This section provides a collection of $d + 2d(r-1)$ measurement vectors which uniquely determine almost every rank- r orthogonal projection. We note that when d is sufficiently large relative to r , this number of measurements fails to satisfy the lower bound in (1). Indeed, an ensemble of measurement vectors can yield ‘‘almost injectivity’’ without yielding injectivity, much like traditional phase retrieval (see [10], for example). The following is the main result of this section:

Theorem 4. *Draw a random subspace uniformly from the complex Grassmannian $\text{Gr}(r, \mathbb{C}^d)$, and let P denote the orthogonal projection onto this subspace. Then the quantities*

$$\|Pe_i\|, \|P(e_i + e_j)\|, \|P(e_i + ie_j)\|$$

with $i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ and $j \in \{1, \dots, r\} \setminus \{i\}$ uniquely determine P with probability 1.

We use the remainder of this section to prove this theorem. First, we prove a couple of lemmas:

Lemma 5. *Let $P: \mathbb{C}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^d$ be linear. Then*

$$\langle P, ab^* + ba^* \rangle_{\text{HS}} = \|P(a+b)\|^2 - \|Pa\|^2 - \|Pb\|^2$$

for every $a, b \in \mathbb{C}^d$.

Proof: Expanding gives

$$(a+b)(a+b)^* = aa^* + ab^* + ba^* + bb^*,$$

and so

$$\begin{aligned} \|P(a+b)\|^2 &= \langle P, (a+b)(a+b)^* \rangle_{\text{HS}} \\ &= \langle P, aa^* \rangle_{\text{HS}} + \langle P, ab^* + ba^* \rangle_{\text{HS}} + \langle P, bb^* \rangle_{\text{HS}} \\ &= \|Pa\|^2 + \langle P, ab^* + ba^* \rangle_{\text{HS}} + \|Pb\|^2. \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging then gives the result. \blacksquare

Lemma 6. *Let U be drawn uniformly from the complex Stiefel manifold $V_r(\mathbb{C}^d)$ of $d \times r$ matrices with orthonormal columns. Then $\det((U_{ij})_{i,j \leq r}) \neq 0$ with probability 1.*

Proof: Let G be a $d \times r$ matrix with iid $\mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ entries, and let U be the matrix of columns gotten by performing Gram–Schmidt on the columns of G , i.e., $G = UR$, where R is an $r \times r$ upper triangular matrix. Since the columns of G are linearly independent with probability 1, the columns of U are orthonormal and R is invertible in the same event. We claim that U has the desired distribution. Assuming for the moment that this is true, let G_1 denote the first r rows from G and similarly U_1 from U . Then

$$\det(U_1) = \det(G_1 R^{-1}) = \det(G_1) \det(R^{-1}) \neq 0$$

with probability 1, as desired.

To verify that U is uniformly distributed over $V_r(\mathbb{C}^d)$, we use the fact that the distribution of G is rotationally invariant. That is, for every $Q \in \text{U}(d)$, $G = UR$ has the same distribution as $QG = QUR$, thereby implying that (U, R) has the same distribution as (QU, R) . Marginalizing these joint distributions then gives that U and QU have the same distribution. Overall, the random matrix U lies in $V_r(\mathbb{C}^d)$ with probability 1, and also has rotationally invariant distribution. At this point, we note that the modular functions of $\text{U}(d)$ and $\text{U}(d-r)$ are both trivial (and hence coincide on $\text{U}(d-r)$), and so the $\text{U}(d)$ -invariant measure on $V_r(\mathbb{C}^d) = \text{U}(d)/\text{U}(d-r)$ is unique up to a multiplicative constant [13]. We therefore conclude that U is uniformly distributed over $V_r(\mathbb{C}^d)$, as desired. \blacksquare

Proof of Theorem 4: Let P_1 denote the first r columns of P . We will demonstrate (i) that the given quantities determine P_1 , and (ii) that P_1 determines P with probability 1.

For (i), first observe that $P_{ii} = e_i^* P e_i = \|P e_i\|^2$. Next, Lemma 5 gives that

$$\begin{aligned} 2 \operatorname{Re} P_{ij} &= P_{ij} + \overline{P_{ij}} \\ &= P_{ij} + P_{ji} \\ &= \langle P, e_i e_j^* + e_j e_i^* \rangle_{\text{HS}} \\ &= \|P(e_i + e_j)\|^2 - \|P e_i\|^2 - \|P e_j\|^2, \end{aligned}$$

and similarly

$$\begin{aligned} 2 \operatorname{Im} P_{ij} &= -i(P_{ij} - \overline{P_{ij}}) \\ &= -iP_{ij} + iP_{ji} \\ &= \langle P, -ie_i e_j^* + ie_j e_i^* \rangle_{\text{HS}} \\ &= \|P(e_i + ie_j)\|^2 - \|P e_i\|^2 - \|P e_j\|^2. \end{aligned}$$

As such, the given quantities determine P_{ij} whenever $j \leq r$, i.e., the entries of P_1 .

For (ii), draw U uniformly from the complex Stiefel manifold $V_r(\mathbb{C}^d)$. Then P has the same distribution as UU^* . Let U_1 denote the first r rows of U . Then P_1 has the same distribution as UU_1^* . By Lemma 6, U_1^* is invertible with probability 1, and so the columns of P_1 are linearly independent in the same event. As such, these columns form a basis for the subspace associated with P , and so $P = P_1(P_1^* P_1)^{-1} P_1^*$, that is, P_1 determines P . \blacksquare

IV. MANIFOLD-CONSTRAINED LEAST SQUARES

This section proposes a general technique for projection retrieval. Consider the matrix manifold

$$\mathcal{M} := \{Q \in \mathbb{C}^{d \times d} : Q^2 = Q, Q^* = Q, \operatorname{rank}(Q) = r\}.$$

This is an embedding of the complex Grassmannian $\text{Gr}(r, \mathbb{C}^d)$ into $\mathbb{C}^{d \times d}$, and we are tasked with recovering some $P \in \mathcal{M}$ given $y_i = \|P x_i\|^2$ for each $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. To this end, we consider the program

$$\hat{P} := \arg \min_{Q \in \mathcal{M}} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\|Q x_i\|^2 - y_i \right)^2. \quad (2)$$

Recalling that $\|Q x_i\|^2 = \langle Q, x x^* \rangle_{\text{HS}}$, we see that the above objective function is quadratic in Q , but since \mathcal{M} is nonlinear, we can expect the constrained optimization to exhibit local minima. However, local minima can be avoided if we initialize a numerical solver sufficiently close to the global minimizer, cf. the Wirtinger flow–based solution to phase retrieval [8].

For this paper, we slightly modify the objective (2) to simplify implementation. We also focus on the case where P is real, thereby allowing the use of a readily available numerical solver. Borrowing ideas from the previous section, we measure $\|P e_i\|^2$ for every $i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ and then we also measure $\|P(e_i + e_j)\|^2$ for some random collection of pairs (i, j) . By Lemma 5, this amounts to observing the diagonal of P as well as a random sample of its off-diagonal entries. Let A denote the symmetric matrix with $A_{ij} = 1$ when $i = j$ or when (i, j) is a member of the random sample, and zero otherwise (i.e., A indicates the sampled entries of P). Given data $Y := A \circ P$, where \circ denotes the entrywise matrix product, we then consider

$$\hat{P} := \arg \min_{Q \in \mathcal{M}'} \|A \circ Q - Y\|_{\text{HS}}^2, \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{M}' is the real counterpart to \mathcal{M} . This revised objective is philosophically identical to (2) since we seek to minimize the 2-norm of deviation from data subject to the matrix manifold; here, we simply organize the data in a manner that is particularly easy to manipulate.

In order to avoid local minima, we seek an initialization that is close to the global minimizer. To this end, consider the orthogonal projection onto the span of the r leading eigenvectors of $A \circ P$. In some sense, $A \circ P$ is simply a noisy version of P , and we can denoise by projecting onto the low-dimensional manifold of rank- r orthogonal projections. As such, we might expect this to be reasonably close to the

global minimizer P , at least if A has enough entries that are 1, i.e., provided n is sufficiently large.

To solve (3), we leverage a freely available Matlab toolbox called Manopt [6]. Specifically, we imposed the manifold constraint by appealing to the built-in `grassmannfactory`, which (redundantly) encodes each point on $\text{Gr}(r, \mathbb{C}^d)$ as a $d \times r$ matrix U with orthonormal columns. Also, we selected the built-in `trustregions` solver, as this is the recommended alternative for smooth optimization. This solver requires both a cost function and a Euclidean gradient (i.e., the gradient of the cost function in matrix space, ignoring the manifold constraint) as inputs:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{cost} &= \|A \circ UU^* - Y\|_{\text{HS}}^2, \\ \text{egrad} &= 4(A \circ UU^* - Y)U. \end{aligned}$$

With this, we solved several instances of projection retrieval. We fixed $d = 50$, and we took $r \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $n \in (50 : 50 : 450)$. For each (r, n) pair, we ran 30 trials of the following experiment: Draw P uniformly at random from \mathcal{M}' , draw $n-d$ random pairs (i, j) to sample the off-diagonal of P , and then attempt to recover P , where successful recovery is declared when $\|\hat{P} - P\|_{\text{HS}} < 10^{-5}$. Figure 1 illustrates the proportion of instances that were successfully recovered.

As expected, it takes more measurements to determine projections of higher rank (at least in the $r \leq d/2$ regime). We find successful recovery over 90% of the time with 250 measurements when $r = 1$, with 300 measurements when $r = 2$, and with 400 measurements when $r = 3$. For comparison, recall that the space of symmetric $d \times d$ matrices has dimension $d(d+1)/2$. Indeed, we find successful recovery when $n = 400 \ll 1275 = d(d+1)/2$. Granted, these simulations are not extensive enough to discern whether n scales like $r(d-r)$, but they certainly demonstrate the feasibility of projection retrieval via manifold-constrained least-squares optimization.

V. DISCUSSION

In this paper, we provided some bounds on the number of measurements necessary and sufficient for projection retrieval, and we also proposed a general technique to algorithmically reconstruct the desired projection. However, several questions remain open. First, we have yet to find an ensemble of $O(r(d-r))$ measurement vectors which yield injectivity. We note that one may pick $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^n$ so that $\{x_i x_i^*\}_{i=1}^n$ forms a basis for the space of self-adjoint $d \times d$ matrices (as in [2]), and this basis will certainly provide complete information about P , but any such basis will have $d^2 \gg r(d-r)$ elements. Rather, we seek an optimally efficient measurement system like those constructed for phase retrieval in [5] and [10]. Second, while we demonstrated the feasibility of projection retrieval by manifold-constrained least-squares optimization, the method currently lacks a performance guarantee. Such a guarantee should illustrate how many measurements are required for the algorithm to succeed. We leave both of these problems for future work.

Fig. 1. Proportion of 30 random 50×50 orthogonal projection matrices P which are recovered from random data by manifold-constrained least-squares optimization using a freely available Matlab toolbox called Manopt [6]. The horizontal axis gives the number of measurements of the form $\|Px\|$ that were collected for random choices of x . The solid curve corresponds to the case where P has rank 1, the dotted curve corresponds to the rank-2 case, and the dash-dotted curve depicts the rank-3 case.

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